

Mental Fatigue Among College And University Students In The State Of West Bengal During Covid 19 Pandemic Period

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 13,2025</p> <p>Accepted: December 14,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mental Fatigue, Covid-19, College and University.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17930424</p>	<p><i>Through the present study, the investigators have tried to study what kind of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students and to find out the concerning their level of Fatigue on the basics of Categories and Streams. The investigators have used the quantitative approach for the present study as the Descriptive method. The Simple Random sampling technique has been used for collecting the sample and the investigators used a questionnaire developed by them. For the analysis of data, investigators have been applied descriptive and inferential statistics. The overall results of the study explored that the level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students is being Moderate in West Bengal. It is revealed that the Girl Students and Rural Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Boy Students and Urban Students. College Student was comparatively more Fatigue than the University Student. Through the present study, It was also found that there is no significant difference among the College and University Students with respect to their Mental Fatigue on the basis of Category and Streams. Researchers use only a limited sample and specific Districts. Researchers collected samples through 'Google form'. The next researcher will study this topic with a large sample and use the mixed method on other Districts or levels.</i></p>

Introduction

Covid-19 is the most burning problem in the world today. This unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic situation has spread to most countries in the world. Most countries have imposed home quarantine, lockdown, curfews to prevent the spread of this infection. All these strategies have forced the people of society to stay at home and maintain social distance (Girdhar et al. 2020). Covid-19 had a significant impact on people's economics, health, education, mental state and social relationships (Moghe et al. 2020). In all countries of the world, People are under house arrest or in quarantine. At the same time, the students have also become house prisoners. Due to this dire situation, various fields of work such as factory, school, college and University have been closed for sine die (Morgul et al. 2020). Students are now sitting at home and taking classes online using various technologies (Rogowsk et al. 2020). As their classes have to be done online mode sitting at home, they have more opportunities to face various mental problems likely mental fatigue, Stress, Anxiety, etc. Mental fatigue is a type of mental condition that disrupts mental health. Loss of physical function and mental ability is called mental fatigue. It is caused by excessive stress and physical activity (Tanaka et al. 2015). Mental fatigue is an unpleasant physical sensation along with emotional, cognitive elements which are not relieved with general strategies to reconstruct energy or power (A. P. Sharaj et al. 2016). It is a type of common system that is associated with a person's neurological disorder (Chaudhuri and Behan 2004). Generally, mental health is a state of harmony and good balance between the individual and the surrounding environment of the world (Palle 2020). Mental fatigue is a state of mind that is characterized by long-term deviation from cognitive activity (Cutsem et al. 2017). Mental fatigue can increase the chances of students making this mistake in the future (McCormick et al. 2012).

Mental fatigue can be also marked by three types.

Subjectively has been increased feelings of tiredness, lack of energy (Boksem 2008) and decrease of motivation (Boksem M. A- 2006). Behaviorally, mental fatigue is acquainted with a decrease in performance on cognitive work (Wascher et al 2014; Marcora et al. 2009). Finally, the physiologic manifestation of mental fatigue has been shown in alterations of brain activity (Cook et al. 2007; Hopstaken et al. 2015). Changes in all these forms of mental fatigue (subjective, behavioral, and physiological) do not have to be present for mental fatigue.

Mental fatigue impacts on various ingredients in daily life. In a large population country as India has no stronger healthcare system. It also disturbance resides in population due to the lack of basic protection elements. It is understood that there is the opportunity of many susceptible psychological factors like a liability to disease, fatigue, stress, intolerance and anxiety, etc (Maebell et al. 2020).

Literature Review

Bachleda and Darhiri (2018) have conducted a study on 'Internet Addiction and Mental and Physical Fatigue. In the present study, the researchers find that Internet addiction has significantly more mental and physical fatigue than students without Internet addiction. Palle, Madhuri (2020) studied 'Impact of Stress on Mental Health in Childhood: During Covid-19' explained that the corona disaster and lockdown conditions are fatal to children's mental health. If the mental state of the children is not taken seriously, the problem will increase further. **Labrague and Ballad (2020)** have conducted a study on "Lockdown fatigue among college Students during the Covid-19 pandemic: predictive role of personal resilience, coping Behaviours, and Health". It reported that moderate levels of lockdown fatigue of college students, with a mean score of 31.54 (out of 50). And also found that Physical exhaustion or tiredness, headaches and body pain decreased motivation and increased worry were the most pronounced manifestations of fatigue. Gender and college year were identified as important predictors of fatigue with lower levels of lockdown fatigue. **Smith, A. P. (2018)** has executed on 'Cognitive Fatigue and the Wellbeing and Academic Attainment of University Students and found that The mental fatigue scores and the established predictors were engaged into regressions with wellbeing score, GPA, course stress and study competency as the outcomes. Participants from years 1 and 2 were found similar levels of wellbeing, attainment and similar associations with interpreters. A P, Sharaj et al. (2016) have conducted a study on 'Fatigue Experienced by Students in a day-long Class: a Survey on Students' and The findings of this study explained that the Main factors impacting students' active listening during lecture class are the not-sufficient number of breaks in a day, a distance of travel, peer pressure and the presence of not-sufficient infrastructure. This study revealed that a student balance his personnel interest and academics further the college should provide an ideal environment as well as allow accomplish the former. Tanaka et al. (2015) studied on 'Effects of Mental Fatigue on Brain Activity and Cognitive Performance: A Magneto encephalography Study' and it indicates that Alpha-frequency band (8-13 Hz) power in the visual cortex had decreased after performing the mental fatigue. The decreased level in the alpha-frequency band power is positively related to the impaired cognitive task performance.

From the above discussion of the previous literature, it is clear that none of the studies have been carried out by any researcher in West Bengal. The review of the studies mentioned above reveals that a small number of the study were undertaken on mental fatigue. So, the researchers chose the study Mental Fatigue of College and University Students in the State of West Bengal during the Covid-19 Pandemic Period.

Delimitations of the Study

A. Geographical Area:

The study was delimited to Kolkata, Hooghly, Purba Bardhaman, Purba Medinipur and Purulia District of West Bengal, India.

B. Level of Education:

The study was delimited to the different College and University students in West Bengal. Among the Post Graduate and Under Graduate students were considered of the present study.

C. Level of Study:

The study was considered at the surface level. Attempts to know the Mental Fatigue were made by an inventory constructed by self-made by the investigator. There is no comparison among interstates and inter districts. The only comparison between the Male and Female students, Rural and Urban students, College and University Students, UR, OBC, SC and ST students, Arts, Science and Commerce students were done.

Objectives of the study:

1. To assess the Mental Fatigue of College and University Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid-19 Pandemic Period.
2. To assess the Mental Fatigue of College Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid-19 Pandemic Period.
3. To assess the Mental Fatigue of University Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
4. To find out the difference between total Boy and total Girl Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
5. To find out the difference between Boy and Girl College Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
6. To find out the difference between Boy and Girl University Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.

7. To find out the difference between Rural and Urban Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
8. To find out the difference between Rural Boys and Rural Girls Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
9. To find out the difference between Urban Boys and Urban Girls Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
10. To find out the difference between Rural Boys and Urban Boys Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
11. To find out the difference between Rural Girls and Urban Girls Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
12. To find out the difference between College and University Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
13. To find out the difference Category among UR, OBC, SC and ST Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
14. To find out the difference among Arts Commerce and Science Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.

Hypothesis of the Study:

1. There is no favorable level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
2. There is no favorable level of Mental Fatigue of College Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
3. There is no favorable level of Mental Fatigue of University Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
4. There is no significant difference between total Boy and total Girl Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
5. There is no significant difference between Boy and Girl College Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
6. There is no significant difference between Boy and Girl University Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
7. There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
8. There is no significant difference between Rural Boys and Rural Girls Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
9. There is no significant difference between Urban Boys and Urban Girls Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
10. There is no significant difference between Rural Boys and Urban Boys Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
11. There is no significant difference between Rural Girls and Urban Girls Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
12. There is no significant difference between College and University Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
13. There is no significant difference Category among UR, OBC, SC and ST Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.
14. There is no significant difference among Arts Commerce and Science Students in respect to their Mental Fatigue in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.

Method

The present study is based on the descriptive survey method.

Participants

All the College and University Students of West Bengal in India comprised the Population of this study. A total of 258 College and University Students of Kolkata, Hooghly, Purba Bardhaman, Purba Medinipur and Purulia District of West Bengal were taken as representative sample of the whole population. Simple Random Sampling technique was used for selecting College and University Students.

The Tool Used

The Mental Fatigue Measuring inventory was used for measuring the Mental Fatigue of College and University Students of West Bengal. It is one kind of self-made questionnaire which applied via online mode through Google form.

Try out

This inventory consists of 27 selective items. The Inventory was constructed on the basis of Likert's Four Point Scale i.e. Always (A), Often (O), Sometimes (S) and Not at all (NA). The value of the coefficient of correlation

of the present research tool was 0.78 which indicates that the tool is reliable and valid. For measuring the validity of the tools, the Expert Judgment Method was used by the researchers. The present researcher has applied SPSS (Version-20) pursued for Mean; S.D.; 't'-Test; ANOVA and Graph.

Scoring Procedure

In the tool there were four options to put tick including Always (A), Often (O), Sometimes (S) and Not at all (NA). Items are given a score of 4, 3, 2 and 1 for Always (A), Often (O), Sometimes (S) and Not at all (NA) respectively.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

H₀₁: There is no favorable level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.

Analysis of the level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students on the basis of cut off point

Table No-1: Shows the Number, Mean and S.D of Total College and University Students

Group	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation
Students	258	64.24	14.71

$$M \pm \sigma$$

$$M + \sigma = 64.24 + 14.71 = 78.95$$

$$M - \sigma = 64.24 - 14.71 = 49.53$$

Table No-2, Show the level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students on the basis of cut off point

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Level of Mental Fatigue
Above- 78.95	44	17.05 %	High
Between- 78.95 to 49.53	179	69.38 %	Moderate
Below- 49.53	35	13.57 %	Low
Total	258	100%	

Figure: 1. Graphical representation of the level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students on the basis of cut off point

H₀₂: There is no favorable level of Mental Fatigue of College Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.

Analysis of the level of Mental Fatigue of College Students on the basis of cut off point

Table No-3: Shows the Number, Mean and S.D of Total College Students

Group	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation
Students	165	64.79	15.27

$$M \pm \sigma$$

$$M + \sigma = 64.79 + 15.27 = 80.06$$

$$M - \sigma = 64.79 - 15.27 = 49.52$$

Table No-4, Show the level of Mental Fatigue of College Students on the basis of cut off point

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Level of Mental Fatigue
Above- 80.06	27	16.36 %	High
Between- 80.06 to 49.52	116	70.30 %	Moderate
Below- 49.52	22	13.34 %	Low
Total	165	100%	

Figure: 2. Graphical representation of the level of Mental Fatigue of College Students on the basis of cut off point

H_{03} : There is no favorable level of Mental Fatigue of University Students in the State of West Bengal during Covid 19 Pandemic Period.

Analysis of the level of Mental Fatigue of University Students on the basis of cut off point

Table No-5: Shows the Number, Mean and S.D of Total University Students

Group	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation
Students	93	63.26	13.70

$M \pm \sigma$

$$M + \sigma = 63.26 + 13.70 = \mathbf{76.96}$$

$$M - \sigma = 63.26 - 13.70 = \mathbf{49.56}$$

Table No-6, Show the level of Mental Fatigue of University Students on the basis of cut off point

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Level of Mental Fatigue
Above-76.96	16	17.20 %	High
Between-76.96 to 49.56	64	68.82 %	Moderate
Below- 49.56	13	13.98 %	Low
Total	93	100%	

Figure: 3. Graphical representation of the level of Mental Fatigue of University Students on the basis of cut off point

Table No-7: Results of t-Test between different groups of College and University Students with regard to their Mental Fatigue.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Difference	S _{ED}	df	t-value	Result
Gender	Boys	60	65.25	14.26	1.32	2.17	256	0.61@	NS
	Girls	198	63.93	14.87					
	College Boys	27	67.89	15.06	3.70	3.21	163	1.15@	NS
	College Girls	138	64.19	15.28					
	University Boys	33	63.09	13.42	0.26	2.97	91	0.09@	NS
	University Girls	60	63.35	13.97					
Residence	Rural	136	65.46	16.05	2.57	1.83	256	1.40@	NS
	Urban	122	62.89	12.99					
	Rural Boys	34	67.94	16.09	3.31	3.17	134	1.04@	NS
	Rural Girls	102	64.63	16.03					
	Urban Boys	26	61.37	10.76	1.47	2.88	120	0.51@	NS
	Urban Girls	96	63.20	13.57					
	Rural Boys	34	67.94	16.09	6.21	3.66	58	1.70@	NS
	Urban Boys	26	61.73	10.76					
	Rural Girls	102	64.36	16.03	1.43	2.12	196	0.68@	NS
	Urban Girls	96	63.20	13.57					
Institution	College	165	64.79	15.27	1.54	1.91	256	0.81@	NS
	University	93	63.26	13.70					

*Significant at 0.05, ** Significant at 0.01 and @ Not Significant [Table Value of 't' against df-256, 163, 91, 134, 120, 58 and 196 at 0.05 level are 1.97, 1.99, 1.98 and 2.00 respectively]

Table No-8: Shows the Number, Mean and S.D of College and University Students of difference groups on the basis of Category and Streams with regard to Mental Fatigue.

Different Aspects	Group/Variable	N	Mean	S.D
Category	U.R	127	63.61	14.88
	OBC	57	63.07	15.63
	SC	67	65.31	13.05
	ST	7	74.86	17.45
Streams	Arts	181	65.39	16.02
	Science	36	62.00	11.56
	Commerce	41	61.12	9.91

Table No-9: Shows the results of ANOVA on different groups of College and University Students with regard to their Mental Fatigue.

Different aspects of	Sum of Squares		Mean Square		F-value
	Between Groups	Within Groups	Between Groups	Within Groups	
Category	994.012	54633.089	331.337	215.091	1.540@
Streams	819.561	54807.539	409.781	214.932	1.907@

*Significant at 0.05, ** Significant at 0.01 and @ Not Significant [Table Value of 'F' against df-3/254 and 2/255 at 0.05 level are 2.6, 3.03 respectively]

Figure 4: Graphical Representation of the Mental Fatigue of College and University Students on the basis of Category.

Figure 4: Graphical Representation of the Mental Fatigue of College and University Students on the basis of Streams.

Testing of H01 and Interpretation:

On the basis of Cut off Point, from *Table No-2*, we can found that out of the total 258 College and University Students, 17.05% of College and University Students have scored Above 78.95, 69.38% of College and University Students have scored Between 78.95 to 49.53 and 13.57% College and University Students have scored Below 49.53 on the Mental Fatigue measuring tools constructed by the investigator for the College and University Students. Therefore, it can be said that the maximum percentage (69.38%) of College and University Students have scored Between 78.95 to 49.53, which indicates that the level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students is being Moderate in West Bengal.

Testing of H02 and Interpretation:

On the basis of Cut off Point, from *Table No-4*, we can found that out of the total 165 College Students, 16.36% of College Students have scored Above 80.06, 70.30% of College Students have scored Between 80.06 to 49.52 and 13.34% College Students have scored Below 49.52 on the Mental Fatigue measuring tools constructed by the investigator for the College Students. Therefore, it can be said that the maximum percentage (70.30%) of College Students have scored Between 80.06 to 49.52, which indicates that the level of Mental Fatigue of College Students is being Moderate in the West Bengal.

Testing of H03 and Interpretation:

On the basis of Cut off Point, from *Table No-6*, we can found that out of the total 93 University Students, 17.20% of University Students have scored Above 76.96, 68.82% of University Students have scored Between

76.96 to 49.56 and 13.98% University Students have scored Below 49.56 on the Mental Fatigue measuring tools constructed by the investigator for the University Students. Therefore, it can be said that the maximum percentage (68.82%) of University Students have scored Between 76.96 to 49.56, which indicates that the level of Mental Fatigue of University Students is being Moderate in the West Bengal.

Testing of H04 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**0.61**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.97 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Boy and Girl Student at the College and University level with respect to their level of Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Girl Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Boy Students.

Testing of H05 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**1.15**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.97 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Boys' and Girls College students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Girls College Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Boys Student.

Testing of H06 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**0.09**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.99 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Boy and Girl of University students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Girls University Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Boys University students.

Testing of H07 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**1.40**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.97 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Rural and Urban students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Rural Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Urban Students.

Testing of H08 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**1.04**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.98 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Rural Boys and Rural Girls students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Rural Boys Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Rural Girls Students.

Testing of H09 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**0.51**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.98 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Urban Boys and Urban Girls Students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Urban Girls Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Urban Boys Students.

Testing of H010 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**1.70**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.98 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Rural Boys and Urban Boys students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Rural Boys Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Urban Boys Student.

Testing of H011 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**0.68**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.97 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Rural Girls and Urban Girls students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Rural Girls Students are comparatively more Fatigue than the Urban Girls Student.

Testing of H012 and Interpretation:

From *Table No- 7*, it is found that the calculated 't'-value (**0.81**) is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance (1.97 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between College and University Students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that College Students are comparatively more Fatigue than University students.

Testing of H013 and Interpretation:

From *Table No-8*, it is observed that the calculated 'F'-ratio is **1.54** which is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the result is not significant and we can say that there is no significant difference among the College and University Students with respect to their Mental Fatigue on the basis of Category. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Testing of *H014* and Interpretation:

From *Table No-8*, it is observed that the calculated 'F'-ratio is **1.91** which is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the result is not significant and we can say that there is no significant difference among the College and University Students with respect to their Mental Fatigue on the basis of Streams. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

The Covid-19 has gradually spread from one country to another. It has been greatly affecting the body and mind of the person. The effects of this dreaded virus have also profoundly affected many aspects of our social relationships. Much more research is needed to bring people back to normal life and free this situation. In this study found that the level of Mental Fatigue of College and University Students is being Moderate in West Bengal. It indicates that there is no significant difference between total Boy and total Girl Students at College and University level with respect to their Mental Fatigue. On the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Girl Students was comparatively more Fatigue than the Boy Students. It found that there is no significant difference between Rural and Urban students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. But Rural Students was comparatively more Fatigue than the Urban Students on the basis of obtained Mean Scores. It also revealed that there is no significant difference between College and University Students with respect to their Mental Fatigue. But the College Student was comparatively more Fatigue than the University Student on the basis of Mean Scores. Finally, it observed that there is no significant difference among the College and university students with respect to their Mental Fatigue on the basis of Category and Streams. So it is safe to say that the same mental fatigue is being created among College and University Students irrespective of race, religion, stream and caste.

So that everyone should be aware of the different pros and cons of this disease. Also, these must have vanished from our life. Mental health is needed to make a person's future beautiful. Mental fatigue makes a person more vulnerable. So every person should use different multimedia means of communication to stay free from mental fatigue in this situation. As a result, the corona virus can be prevented by maintaining social distance. From the beginning, there has been a change in the behavior of different types of people. The current government has said it will continue to fight for the survival of the virus in daily life.

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